

Research Intelligence Expert Group - Roadmap of Research Priorities

Portage Research Intelligence Expert Group
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Introduction

The Portage Research Intelligence Expert Group (RIEG) was formed in May 2016 to develop a high-level roadmap of research priorities on the topic of research data management (RDM). From September 2016 to October 2017, expert group members worked together to conceptualize an approach, and then gather and organize public information on various topics pertaining to RDM, originating from both Canada and abroad, in order to identify subject areas needing new knowledge and further exploration.

In order to understand the current research landscape, RIEG members conducted an environmental scan focused on select outputs of regulatory, governmental, and professional bodies, whose work is similar to the scope and outreach of Portage. Over 100 English and French-language publications, including reports, best practice documents, articles, and other documentation were identified for review. Content and scope analyses of compiled sources were conducted through the application of a novel taxonomy developed by RIEG to support the description and organization of sources according to key subject areas. The taxonomy was applied independently to each publication to identify the primary topics. To increase the reliability of subject classifications, all classifications were conducted independently by two reviewers, with a third independent reviewer resolving any inconsistencies.

Subject areas addressed in the reviewed publications were subsequently examined through both Canadian and international lenses to understand the current RDM landscape, determine gaps, and prioritize areas for further research. The gaps and recommendations listed in this roadmap are intended as general suggestions to 1) describe the current state of publications relating to a range of research data management topics, and 2) inform the future work of RIEG and/or the broader Portage Network. Recommendations made in this roadmap are not intended to be prescriptive. As well, in the time since work on this roadmap was started, various Portage Expert Groups have already begun addressing some of the recommendations, many of which are listed in the roadmap table.

Following the publication of this roadmap, RIEG will oversee the formation of new working groups that will undertake specific studies to address some of the recommendations presented in collaboration with other Portage Expert Groups and stakeholders (e.g., the Tri-Agency, consortia, etc.), as appropriate.

Project Timeline

- The taxonomy was completed July 2017. Taxonomy document with added definitions completed November 2018.
- The selection of publications began in September 2016 and was completed October 2017.
- Taxonomy application to the select publications by two reviewers was conducted October and November 2017.
- The 3rd party review of the application of the taxonomy to compiled resources was conducted between November 2017 and January 2018.
- Analysis of the results of the taxonomy application were conducted between January 2018 and January 2019.
- The roadmap of research priorities was completed July 2019.

Layout of document

The full roadmap is presented as a table organized into 5 key research topics: Curation, Services, Sharing and Reuse, Policy and Law, and Information Technologies. For each of these topics, the current state is described in relation to the Canadian context. Gaps in the information available for the topic are identified, as are recommendations for research action. Preceding the table is a summary of research priorities for RIEG.

Summary of Priorities

In review of the information available, RIEG has generated a list of priorities to guide the expert group to January 2021. While CARL/Portage has sources available to address some areas, some of these sources may now be out of date, and RIEG may wish to assess whether updates are needed. Across all topics – curation, services, sharing and reuse, policy and law, and IT infrastructure – there were some recurring observations of gaps in priority areas that Portage may wish to address. It was noted that few of the reviewed publications provided discipline-specific guidance needed by researchers to carry out RDM related tasks, and there also needs to be greater emphasis on working with confidential and sensitive data. Also noted is a lack of Canadian-focused materials and the need for the creation of French language materials as a priority for all areas. International materials are useful for librarians and researchers, but these resources miss key legal and policy information relevant to Canada, as well as any related Canadian contacts or services that could be useful.

There is a general need for introductory guides, as other bodies with similar functions to Portage are currently offering these. Though this means that there are guides already available internationally, generating these could help researchers in Canada identify Portage as the national “network of expertise” for research data management information and assistance. In the creation of such introductory guides for librarians and researchers, work will be done in collaboration with other Expert Groups with RIEG offering support for any background research needed.

RIEG's priority will be to perform research tasks to bridge gaps. This may include research to help broaden Portage initiatives, or specific tasks to assist other expert group priorities or areas of responsibility. Below are specific priority areas, identified by topic, for further examination.

Curation

The state of data curation is changing rapidly with the creation and evolution of standards and best practices being set by both domain-based communities and national organizations. In Canada, guidance is needed to support researchers with developing curation skills, especially discipline-specific guidance for STEM and the Arts and Humanities. RIEG has identified key gaps in the Canadian RDM curation context, and recommends the following actions:

1. Development of appropriate introductory materials, best practices, and templates to support the training and work of stakeholders related to data curation for STEM and the Arts and Humanities.
 - 1.1. Repurpose, where appropriate, the topics which are well covered by other jurisdictions or bodies.
 - 1.2. Contribute to the literature on topics which are not well covered in the selected literature, by creating guidance for our stakeholders.
2. Survey of existing services and policies to support stakeholders in providing curation.
 - 2.1. Understand what measures are important in costing - about which little exists in the global literature - and determine established ways to calculate RDM costs that could be replicated.
 - 2.2. Analyze existing data selection and appraisal for retention plans or policies; conduct research with the aim of helping institutions develop their own selection and appraisal policies.

Services

In Canada, services to support researchers in managing their research data are in the early stages of development. At present, the landscape of services and service providers at national, regional, and institutional levels is complex and rapidly evolving. Clarity around user needs, stakeholder responsibilities, and existing services and service providers is needed in order to map out clear and simple paths to services and support for the benefit of researchers and their data. Notwithstanding this lack of clarity, RIEG has identified key gaps in the Canadian RDM service context, and recommends the following actions be prioritized:

1. Survey of existing services and capacity to support RDM at institutional, regional, and national scales.
 - 1.1. Survey RDM services provided by Canadian research institutions; including, but not limited to, teaching, infrastructure, services, and resources.
 - 1.2. Survey how Canadian research institutions are developing and allocating human, infrastructure, and fiscal resources to develop and support RDM services.
 - 1.3. Inventory existing regional and national RDM services to develop a system diagram of existing stakeholders and services.
2. Assistance, where appropriate, in the research and/or development of tools and guidance to support the training of a wide range of stakeholders on topics in RDM, especially the development and evaluation of data management plans. Specific areas include:
 - 2.1. Subject-specific DMP templates for wide adoption and adaptation by diverse research communities.
 - 2.2. Exemplar DMPs to be leveraged by diverse research communities.
 - 2.3. Assessment and evaluation criteria for DMPs, based on empirical evidence supporting the value and utility of DMPs.
3. Work on outreach and promotion of the benefits of RDM, to facilitate successful adoption of best practices and use of emerging services being developed nationally, regionally, and institutionally (especially in relation to developing successful models for raising awareness and incentivising adoption).

Sharing and Reuse

With a few exceptions, data sharing has not been mandated by granting bodies at the federal level in Canada. As changes are made to funding mandates in this area, researchers will need direction to ensure data that is shared is done so effectively. Nationally-coordinated infrastructure efforts are underway to facilitate data sharing and discovery, but best practice guidelines and disciplinary considerations need to be elaborated for researchers, especially related to sensitive and confidential data. RIEG has identified key gaps existing within data sharing and reuse, and recommends the following actions be prioritized:

1. Gaining insight into data sharing and data reuse practices within Canada.
 - 1.1. Engage with disciplinary communities within Canada and examine disciplinary practices.
 - 1.2. Examine sharing workflows and related research systems.
 - 1.3. Assess reuse of Canadian created or hosted data.
2. Continuing work with national infrastructure efforts related to data sharing.
 - 2.1. Create researcher-oriented resources for data sharing decisions.
 - 2.2. Examine ways metrics and data citation can be incorporated into national efforts.
 - 2.3. Assess Canadian data discoverability and offer guidance to researchers for preparing data, selecting metadata standards and repository options for optimal discovery.

Policy and Law

In Canada, there are clear federal and provincial laws related to working with personal information, intellectual property, and copyright. Canada is also preparing for changes in federal funding mandates related to data which may affect both researchers and institutions. Assessing readiness and understanding community needs will help prepare for changing expectations and new responsibilities. Providing informed guidance to help navigate the legal and policy environment related to research data will be important in helping with compliance. Some of the ways RIEG can assist is to develop background research and/or material on the following topics:

1. Training materials.
 - 1.1. Contextualize information needs to federal and provincial laws.
 - 1.2. Provide guidelines and recommendations for working with confidential and sensitive data.
2. Assessing and monitoring of Canadian policy environment at the federal funding level.
 - 2.1. Undertake an assessment of policies and information related to strategic planning and RDM service development within research organizations and post-secondary institutions.
 - 2.2. Perform an environmental scan of Canadian institutional and library policies and/or strategies regarding RDM.
 - 2.3. Conduct a survey to assess progress in developing institutional strategies as a requirement of the anticipated Tri-Agency research data management policy.
 - 2.4. Measure engagement with Portage strategic planning documents.

Information Technologies

Some countries and entities are developing IT infrastructure at national or consortial levels and others are approaching this institution by institution. Canada is building its capabilities for data repositories at the national level, and is building on and contributing to globally produced software tools and applications. Both clarity and guidance in developing or using IT infrastructure is needed therefore RIEG has identified the following activities it could work on or contribute to:

1. Investigation of the state of repositories needed for both storage and publication.
 - 1.1. Investigate opportunities to increase active data storage, particularly for big data.
 - 1.2. Conduct a needs assessment of repository features necessary to support sensitive data.
 - 1.3. Investigate ways to make the publication of big data easier (Compute Canada is a potential partner in this).
2. Investigation of tools and applications.
 - 2.1. Investigate opportunities to connect infrastructure and to support active, repository, and archival storage.
 - 2.2. Review or catalogue various recommended tools and applications deemed useful at different points of the data lifecycle (and for different disciplines).
3. Investigation of the current state of Trusted Digital Repository (TDR) certification of Canadian data repositories.
 - 3.1. Create resources to educate repository managers and other stakeholders in becoming certified with recognized bodies such as: [CoreTrustSeal](#), [Trusted Repository Audit Checklist \(TRAC\)](#) and [ISO 16363](#) (also known as [The Trusted Digital Repository Checklist \(TDR\)](#)).
 - 3.2. Investigate opportunities to support repositories in becoming TDRs.

Roadmap of Research Priorities

The following tables detail the results of the analysis and will guide RIEG into research activities that may be important to consider. The gaps noted are those that were identified in the specific publications reviewed by RIEG and detailed above; other sources, not examined, may address some of this information. The recommendations are broad suggestions of ways to bridge these gaps. Gaps and recommendations are organized by topic according to the RIEG taxonomy used to assess the body of source material. Since the analysis was completed, other Expert Groups may have already undertaken work to address some of these gaps.

Curation

Current State

The state of data curation is changing rapidly with the creation and evolution of standards and best practices being set by both domain-based communities and national organizations, relating to data management planning guidelines, metadata standards, storage infrastructure, and other topics.

The topics of **Data Management Plans (DMPs)** and the **Data Curation Lifecycle** are well-covered in the literature. Other topics on specific aspects of data curation are less-well covered.

Overall, there are many documents at the introductory level, followed by checklists and best practices.

Regarding literature at the disciplinary level, the social sciences are well represented; whereas the arts and humanities are less well covered, and the STEM (science, technology, engineering, mathematics) disciplines are poorly covered.

No literature was identified in which topics of **Costing**, **Migration**, **Ingestion**, and **Digitization** were a major focus.

Canadian Context

In Canada, the **Data Curation Lifecycle** is well covered in the published literature, but there is scant information on all other topics that cover specific aspects of data curation. The documents retrieved were mostly reports and policies, rather than more practical items such as checklists, templates or introductory guides.

Similar to the international sources, the STEM disciplines are poorly represented in the Canadian publication outputs on **Data Curation** topics. Most discipline-specific literature in Canada pertains to the Social Sciences, while the Arts and Humanities have some information written about their curation needs.

Gaps and Recommendations

Gaps	Recommendations
<p>General</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In Canada, all subtopics are missing practical items such as glossaries, checklists, how-to guides, templates, and introductory guides. These are needed to support researchers with developing curation skills. • Information needs to be adapted to the Canadian context. • Discipline-specific guidance for STEM, and Arts and Humanities subjects is lacking 	<p>General</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create discipline-specific guidance where it is needed, beginning with STEM, and the Arts and Humanities. • Repurpose existing information from other countries or entities for the Canadian context. • Given the rapidly evolving landscape of data curation in Canada, some previously published documents by CARL/Portage likely need updating.
<p>1) File formats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introductory information and best practices on choosing which file formats to use to gather, transfer and store research data is missing. 	<p>1) File formats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create introductory information and best practices.
<p>2) Privacy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is no guidance for the Canadian context. 	<p>2) Privacy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create introductory materials and also produce guidelines or best practices, which take into consideration differences in provincial requirements.
<p>3) Security</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is virtually no information available on this topic at both the Canadian and global level in the sources examined. 	<p>3) Security</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create introductory materials to the topics and also produce guidelines or best practices.
<p>4) Storage and backup</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is not a lot of information available in Canada or worldwide. A gap on best practices exists at the global level. 	<p>4) Storage and backup</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create introductory and best practice information for Canada and make it scalable or usable on a global level.
<p>5) Preservation and archiving</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This area has been identified as a training gap by TEG. • In Canada there are no guidance documents for researchers, and also no advanced technical documents relating to preservation, although there is 	<p>5) Preservation and archiving</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create introductory materials to the topics and also produce guidelines or best practices.

Gaps	Recommendations
<p>work being done to develop preservation infrastructure . There is information available on both of these topics from an international perspective, with guidelines and also discipline-specific information.</p>	
<p>6) Data management plans</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Additional guidance is needed for the Canadian context. The current guidance available on the DMP Assistant offers this at an introductory level, but as policies evolve and institutions begin to adapt DMPs for their own specific contexts and capacities, more specific guidance will be needed. • DMP guidance information from a discipline-specific context is a gap that needs to be assessed and addressed. 	<p>6) Data management plans</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide introductory documentation on the purpose of DMPs; provide documentation on how to write a DMP (best practices). Work is being done by the Training Expert Group (TEG). • Assess recommended areas in a DMP that should be addressed by institutional guidance. • Determine if guidance should be offered according to discipline, or by topic (e.g. file format). Or, is there one set of best practices that could be illustrated with discipline-specific examples?
<p>7) Costing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a gap in information or assessment worldwide and in Canada. 	<p>7) Costing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determine which measures would be most important to understand. • Determine established ways to calculate RDM costs that could be replicated.
<p>8) Data curation lifecycle</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is plenty of information, both globally and in Canada on this topic that provides a general overview of the data curation lifecycle, however, there is limited discipline-specific information. • The literature consists of introductory guides, training papers, best practices and a glossary. 	<p>8) Data curation lifecycle</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keep all introductory literature current. • Further work on workflows within the data curation lifecycle.
<p>9) Data collection and analysis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is one guide from ICPSR on social science data preparation throughout the lifecycle, but no information from the Canadian sources analyzed, and also nothing covering other disciplines. Outside of the sources, the DMP Assistant has some guiding documentation to consider when creating a data management plan, but this could be augmented with other practical and more detailed information/guides for researchers. 	<p>9) Data collection and analysis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop discipline-specific data preparation guides based on best practices.

Gaps	Recommendations
<p>10) Metadata/ documentation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is insufficient documentation emphasizing and illustrating the importance of metadata and documentation in data curation. • There is a lack of exemplars and templates that demonstrate good practices for metadata/documentation creation and application. 	<p>10) Metadata/ documentation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create introductory information and best practices, and exemplars and templates. • Evaluate how metadata standards used in Canadian repositories reflect discipline-specific standards.
<p>11) Metadata: acquisition/harvesting.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is scant information regarding introductory information and best practices both for Canada and globally. The Metadata Working Group of the Portage Data Discovery Expert Group has completed a metadata crosswalk that was developed for the Federated Research Data Repository (FRDR); this adds to the body of available publications. 	<p>11) Metadata acquisition / harvesting</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create/re-purpose introductory information and best practices.
<p>12) Versioning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is not a lot of information available in Canada or worldwide - only one document discusses versioning in depth and it is on citation. • There is no or little information at the global level. 	<p>12) Versioning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide introductory information to fill the literature gap.
<p>13) Migration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a gap in information or assessment worldwide and in Canada. 	<p>13) Migration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct research to understand best practices and general information that should be available.
<p>14) Ingestion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a gap in information or assessment worldwide and in Canada. 	<p>14) Ingestion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct research to understand best practices and general information that should be available.
<p>15) Digitization</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a gap in information or assessment worldwide and in Canada. 	<p>15) Digitization</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gather information on data digitization technologies available and projects happening in Canada. • Conduct research to understand best practices and general information that should be available.
<p>16) Selection and appraisal for retention</p>	<p>16) Selection and appraisal for retention</p>

Gaps	Recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• There are two good resources covering this topic from the DCC. This could be an important gap to address in Canada as we prepare for more robust retention requirements from the federal agencies, and researchers, as well as institutions who will have to make these types of decisions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Conduct research on recommended practices and considerations.• Analyze existing plans or policies.

Services

Current State

In terms of national services, in many Western countries, various groups are developing services to support RDM, in terms of education, curation, or repository and archival storage. Meanwhile, at the level of individual research institutions, key stakeholders across research campuses are either augmenting existing services, or developing new offerings to support researchers with RDM.

Documents covering **Service Development** tend to focus on higher education institutions and developing services for researchers, including guides on how to identify researchers' RDM requirements and needs.

Within these sources, **Assessment/Evaluation** focuses on repositories or IT infrastructure as a service, as well as identifying researcher requirements to guide the development of RDM services.

Regarding **Training and Education**, the focus tends to be on upskilling for library and university employees to be able to provide RDM services to researchers.

Case studies and examples are available from the UK and Australia that discuss developing a **Strategic Plan** for supporting RDM. [The Digital Curation Centre](#) has one document that covers **Institutional Support** in the form of IT infrastructure.

Canadian Context

The development of RDM services in Canada is still in the early stages. The Canadian sources examined focus on identifying researcher needs as well as **Roles and Responsibilities** for various institutional stakeholders (e.g. administration, systems/IT, libraries, researchers).

Portage, convened by the Canadian Association of Research Libraries, is one national organization in the Canadian landscape which is focused on developing a network of expertise for the purpose of building local capacity for RDM in research institutions across the country.

Within Portage, the work of the Canadian RDM Survey Consortium may help identify potential RDM services for researchers. As well, the Training Expert Group has gathered a listing of Canadian university RDM websites and guides, and has come up with recommendations for improving RDM training from a national perspective.

Canada has more documents related to **Training and Education** than are available internationally. Most notably there are more case studies of training for researchers and students, not just library and university staff.

Similar to other regions, **Assessment/Evaluation** has been focused on identifying researchers' RDM needs and readiness to meet requirements (such as the UBC Research Data Discovery Manual and SSHRC's DMP pilot workshop). However, RDM services in Canada may not be mature enough for evaluation.

Portage has released one document that discusses **Outreach** as part of RDM services. While not directly outreach, UBC’s Research Data Discovery Manual is meant as a guide to conducting an RDM consultation with interview questions, but not much has been written about outreach and RDM consultations.

Canada has more documents focused on developing **Strategic Plans** for RDM than international comparators. Canadian documents include a lot of benchmarking and surveying the landscape in RDM as part of strategic planning. This may be due in part to the fact that Canada has been preparing for the release of a draft policy for RDM from the federal funding agencies, which will require services and infrastructure to support anticipated researcher requirements.

Gaps and Recommendations

Gaps	Recommendations
<p>General</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Much of the available literature focuses on assessing readiness and planning for future services, with not as much focus on examining current service providings, or on evaluating effectiveness or service models. • Consideration of institutional capacity is missing from the available literature. What local services are required, what services can be tackled consortially or nationally, and how to best prioritize service areas are topics that have not been addressed. 	<p>General</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide guidance for the assessment of existing RDM services. • Prioritize core services, and evaluate approaches for institutions with limited capacity to provide RDM to support researchers.
<p>1) Service development</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staffing model for RDM services is a challenge, especially for libraries. There is only one document addressing staffing, which is published by the Data Curation Network. 	<p>1) Service development</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify top resources and readings to help RDM service providers get started with service development (e.g. how to identify RDM needs, info about different types of services that can be offered, etc.). • Investigate potential staffing model or organizational structure for RDM services. • Research or develop ways to calculate return on investment. • Document which services are offered at Canadian institutions. • Document how Canadian institutions are engaging with RDM (staffing, working groups, committees, units, etc.). • Consideration and evaluation of commercial service packages.
<p>2) Assessment/ evaluation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guidelines for assessing and evaluating DMPs are not covered, though there is some current research being conducted in this area (see research from Carlson et al.). 	<p>2) Assessment/evaluation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine DMP evaluation tools or reports from other countries.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other RDM services may not be mature enough for evaluation. 	
<p>3) Training and education</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There were no sources addressing RDM curriculum and courses in LIS/MIS/MLIS/iSchools. 	<p>3) Training and education</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct a survey to see what is being taught about RDM in LIS/MIS/MLIS/iSchools • Examine job postings and requirements to identify RDM skills needed by new professionals.
<p>4) Outreach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very few of the resources reviewed addressed outreach. 	<p>4) Outreach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investigate successful outreach and awareness strategies used by international and Canadian organizations. • Organize a roundtable discussion at a future RDM event that would allow participants to share outreach strategies and approaches.
<p>5) Data purchasing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very few documents are available about purchasing third party data. 	<p>5) Data purchasing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine data purchasing from the aspect of how it might relate to data sharing (licenses). • Examine data collection policies as a piece of larger institutional data policies.
<p>6) Institutional support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very few of the resources reviewed addressed institutional support, including policies, staffing, and infrastructure for RDM throughout the data lifecycle. 	<p>6) Institutional support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct further research to identify existing and/or potential institutional support for RDM. • Identify the key stakeholders at various institutions, their roles and responsibilities in supporting RDM. • Compile a list of university-wide initiatives in place to support RDM needs. • Identify barriers/limitations that may be placed on certain services.
<p>7) Developing strategic plan</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Canada has lots of information that considers developing strategic plans. The Institutional Research Data Management (RDM) Strategy Working Group is already working on this from a Portage perspective and has published guidance documents. However, we do not know how institutions are engaging with the documents and what point individual institutions across Canada are at with RDM strategic plans. 	<p>7) Developing strategic plan</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Document the way institutions are engaging with Portage institutional strategy documents. • Conduct an assessment of Canadian institutional and library strategic plans regarding RDM.

Sharing and Reuse

Current State

Several countries have federal mandates in place related to data sharing. Some include coordinated national efforts for data sharing infrastructure and/or for the dissemination of general best practice information for researchers or developers/repository managers. Developed in Europe, the FAIR principles are a set of guiding principles for data stewardship that seek to make data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable for the benefit of all stakeholders.

Generally, there is a mix of documents providing systems/infrastructure assessment or implementation perspectives, and guides for understanding concepts or best practices. There is not a lot of focus on specific domains or types of data (although we did review one publication on social science data and one on sensitive data).

Some aspects of data sharing appear to have a larger worldwide presence outside of Canada – these mostly relate to **Data Reuse** and mechanisms for reuse (including **Data Citation** and **Persistent Identifiers**).

Worldwide (including Canada) there is no information available on **Metrics** and **Visualization**. As data sharing becomes more common, these topics may need better representation.

Canadian Context

Data sharing has not been mandated at a federal level in Canada yet (with a couple exceptions for health and certain polar data), so the lack of national coordination of data sharing efforts or information available may reflect this. Despite this, Canada has identified a need for a national digital infrastructure. Currently, Canada has DataCite Canada, and national infrastructure efforts related to data sharing such as [Dataverse](#) and [the Federated Research Data Repository \(FRDR\)](#).

Canadian publications reviewed were related to **Data Sharing** and **Data Repositories (not institutional)** topics in this category. Documents focus on general guidelines for data sharing, such as data deposit and metadata, which may indicate a good foundation for national efforts. Assessment of repositories was reviewed in one publication, but there was an absence of information relating to other aspects of data sharing in the reviewed literature.

Globally (outside of Canada) there is a greater availability of assessment and best practice information. There is also more training information both generally and by specific domain/data type, as well as a better coverage of more facets of data sharing both from the infrastructure perspective and the researcher perspective.

Gaps and Recommendations

Gaps	Recommendations
<p>General</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Best practices are lacking across all data sharing subtopics for Canada. • Globally outside of Canada there is a higher availability of training information both generally and by specific domain/data type (one publication on social sciences, one on sensitive data). • Information also needs to be contextualized to the Canadian context (law). 	<p>General</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create introductory guides as well as guidelines for best practices within the Canadian context (this may need to be specific for each province if related to law). • Break out topics by discipline or type of data when practices differ. • Make research and/or documents applicable nationally, and consider addressing all topics for the infrastructure/development side as well as the researcher side. • Examine FAIR principles and how this could be incorporated in the Canadian context (e.g. best practices).
<p>1) Data sharing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Canada does not have the same amount of information available as other countries, both in regards to preparing data for sharing , and the infrastructure side. More resources to help guide researchers may be needed. 	<p>1) Data sharing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recommend best practices or standards related to RDM and data sharing. • Examine the need for more training material for researchers. • Look into RDM and data sharing workflows.
<p>2) Data reuse</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global documents address the legal aspects of preparing data for reuse. • There is a gap in the basic information available for researchers in Canada. 	<p>2) Data reuse</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine ways to address how to think about data reuse and the basic things to know when starting to think about RDM related to reuse, such as working with sensitive or confidential data, intellectual property rights, and commercial interests, as well as best practices for preparing data specifically for reuse purposes. • Consider ways to assess Canadian created or hosted data reuse.
<p>3) Data citation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There seems to be no apparent gap outside of incorporating data citation into general training. • Version control information may need to be considered. 	<p>3) Data citation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify citation training material and/or resources that lack guidance and formatting on data citation. • Create standard language or citation format examples. • Create a one-pager on data citation styles. • Investigate ongoing efforts in the area of education of data citation, and look into efforts that advocate for standard data citation formats (style guides, publisher format, citation management systems).

Gaps	Recommendations
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine ways standardized data citation could be incorporated into existing infrastructure and future plans (e.g. providing recommended data citation from metadata, citation exports in different style formats).
<p>4) Metrics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a gap in examined information sources available worldwide and in Canada. 	<p>4) Metrics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine metrics related to data more thoroughly before further priorities can be identified. • Investigate ways in which metrics could be incorporated into Canadian platforms. • Look into the “Make Data Count” project that was recently announced regarding shared access of usage metrics for data repositories.
<p>5) Attribution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Canada is missing an introductory explanation for researchers. There are no sources dedicated directly to attribution, but in two sources it falls as a subsection within related discussions of licencing and interoperability. 	<p>5) Attribution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider more information on licensing data, including relevance to Canadian copyright law. • Examine role of FAIR principles as well as ORCID for attribution.
<p>6) Visualization</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a lack of information available in general on this topic. 	<p>6) Visualization</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine visualization capabilities within Canadian repositories (assess what is available).
<p>7) Discoverability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a lack of practical information for researchers to understand or enable discovery. • There is also no discussion of the assessment of data discovery. 	<p>7) Discoverability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide information on best practices for researchers to enable data discovery, both for preparing data and data sharing options (metadata, repository choices, linking, etc). • Assess Canadian data discoverability. • Examine discoverability of datasets within Dataverse or FRDR (e.g. metadata inclusion, guidance needed).
<p>8) Data papers/data journals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a gap in a description of what data publishing options exist (both in Canada and internationally), and the recognition of non-traditional research outputs and options for more research exposure (such as data papers or journals). 	<p>8) Data papers/data journals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create guides or best practices. • There may be an opportunity to examine publisher recommendations related to data papers/journals and associated or affiliated repository options.

Gaps	Recommendations
<p>9) Data repositories</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Little information is available to help researchers select or navigate data repositories from a Canadian or a disciplinary perspective. 	<p>9) Data repositories</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine the need for researcher-oriented best practices, checklists or directional information for where to deposit.
<p>10) Permanent identifiers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This is discussed in fair depth from international sources in regards to infrastructure as well as related to things such as citation. None of the Canadian sources reviewed include specific information on permanent identifiers. 	<p>10) Permanent identifiers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a general guide on permanent identifiers for researchers.

Policy and Law

Current State

Countries have individual laws relating to the handling of personal information, intellectual property, and copyright. When information regarding how to navigate within a legal framework is readily available and presented in a clear manner, it is easier for those working with data or data infrastructure to navigate. In addition to national or regional laws, there are also policy frameworks being published by institutions, funders and publishers. Having established requirements from each of these entities can help lay out expectations of good data practices.

Within the sources examined, there are mostly best practices and reports on policy and law topics, with a lot of introductory information to educate on the principles and expectations within the legal and policy frameworks. For the most part these sources address the topics from a general perspective, with the sources intended for either researchers working with data, administration or librarians thinking about institutional policies, or those working in technical infrastructure.

Across the examined sources, there is little information available on **Compliance, Informed Consent, and Journal Requirements**. As the RDM policy environment matures, we may see more harmonized requirements and greater compliance assessment.

Canadian Context

Like other countries, Canada has clear federal and provincial laws related to working with personal information, intellectual property, and copyright.

The Canadian federal funding agencies do not currently have harmonized policies related to research data, however this may be changing in the near future. A draft policy was released in the summer of 2018 that outlines potential greater requirements surrounding data management plans, data sharing, data preservation, and institutional responsibilities (including institutional policies).

The Canadian sources examined discuss **Funding Policy** and **Institutional Policy** subtopics. A greater range of subtopics are discussed in greater detail in international sources. The only subtopic that Canadian sources discuss more than the international sources is **Funding Policy**, and perhaps this is because Canada is currently preparing for the aforementioned changes in federal funding mandates.

Gaps and Recommendations

Gaps	Recommendations
<p>General</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a gap in Canadian federal funding policies in comparison to other countries. • Outside of Canada there is a higher availability of general educational resources to help researchers understand concepts, as well as more information to assist with infrastructure considerations (such as interoperability). • Information also needs to be contextualized to the Canadian/provincial context (law). 	<p>General</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify specific topics where introductory training material should be created. • Develop best practices or guides for Canadian repositories.
<p>1) Compliance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a gap in information on assessment worldwide and in Canada. 	<p>1) Compliance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate methods of measuring or assessing compliance, with the objective of understanding how institutions and funders can encourage compliance.
<p>2) Ethics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a gap for a general introduction to the concept/topic, but often more detailed information would be found within Canadian institutions' ethics review boards. 	<p>2) Ethics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine need for general guidance on ethics relating to the Canadian context. • Explore integration potentials for ethics management systems (e.g. how to highlight/flag insufficient or deficient data curation considerations in ethics submissions).
<p>3) Informed consent</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topic is mentioned, but not as a main topic addressed by the selected sources, internationally or in Canada. This topic may be addressed in more detail by ethics/administrative boards, but it could be helpful for consideration for other areas such as in the data management planning stages. 	<p>3) Informed consent</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine possibilities for general guidance relating to Canadian law.
<p>4) Intellectual property</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More introductory information is necessary to explain concepts, considerations and implications. 	<p>4) Intellectual property</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform a scan of the type of general information that needs to be available.
<p>5) Deposit licenses</p>	<p>5) Deposit licenses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct an examination of Canadian repository deposit licenses or agreements.

Gaps	Recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International sources have very basic introductory information about deposit licenses/agreements. There is a gap in sources providing best practices or guides for drafting a deposit license for repository managers – it could be an area to pay attention to, especially regarding national efforts for digital infrastructure, as well as for institutional responsibility in anticipation of funding requirements. 	
<p>6) User licenses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International sources have detailed information on licensing data and understanding different types of licences and schemas, examples of recommendations for both researchers and repository managers. 	<p>6) User licenses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform a scan of the type of general information that needs to be available.
<p>7) Institutional policy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International sources have practical strategic documents/guides detailing why RDM is important, the facets to consider, and how to develop or implement RDM policy at an institution. Documents in Canada focus on understanding the policy landscape and address policy planning from a wider, national strategic perspective. 	<p>7) Institutional policy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determine how the Portage institutional strategy documents are being used and provide recommendations for improvement. • Assess content and coverage of Canadian institutional policies related to research data. • Identify or create exemplars of Canadian institutional policies related to research data.
<p>8) Funding policy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Canadian sources about funding policies discuss the Canadian landscape, important principles, a gap analysis, and assessment of readiness, while international sources reviewed detail the funding policies that already exist and how to meet the requirements. The gap here currently might just be the lack of strong (i.e. enforceable) Canadian funding policies related to research data. 	<p>8) Funding policy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>No action suggested for the moment, while Canadian research funding agencies are developing their draft RDM policy.</i>
<p>9) Journal policy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While there is research and literature available regarding journal policies, the reviewed sources did not address this topic. 	<p>9) Journal policy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>No action suggested at the moment.</i>

Information Technologies

Current State

The examined resources related to IT infrastructure focus on **Institutional Repositories** (IR) and associated hardware or software. Some countries and entities are developing infrastructure at national or consortial levels and others approach this institution by institution. There are also efforts being made towards the interoperability of platforms and the development of **Tools and Applications**.

The majority of examined sources focused on case studies and reports, with emphasis on getting an IR up and running, using particular software or hardware.

Trusted Digital Repositories were mentioned as recommended services, and **Tools and Applications** were mentioned as parts of service provision.

Examined resources with explicit mention of **High Performance Computing** (HPC) centres and cloud computing were poorly represented. However, we do note that actual computing power and the server location of repositories is generally not represented in the sources reviewed.

Canadian Context

Canada has produced some high level literature regarding **Institutional Repositories** which identify gaps in national infrastructure and describe available services. To that end, several projects have been initiated, including: [Federated Research Data Repository](#) (FRDR) and [Dataverse North](#) (DVN). FRDR is a national platform for the storage and discovery of Canadian research data. DVN is a project contributing to a community of practice for libraries who want to use the [Dataverse](#) repository platform, coordinating efforts at a national level

Scholars Portal has gone through the process of obtaining **Trusted Digital Repository** status for their journal repository, but that process has not been done for Dataverse yet.

Gaps and Recommendations

Gaps	Recommendations
General <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The examined literature generally focuses on repositories and specific hardware and software. Non-proprietary or general information at the technical and non-technical levels is in short supply.	General <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Provide introductory, general information for both technical and non-technical audiences.
1) Cloud computing <ul style="list-style-type: none">• There is a gap in examined information available worldwide and in Canada.	1) Cloud computing <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Provide introductory general information about cloud computing.

Gaps	Recommendations
<p>2) Institutional Repositories</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There appears to be a gap in the general description and purpose of IRs. • RDA has recommendations on linking data from various repositories and another on linking journal articles with data. The Canadian perspective lacks this information. 	<p>2) Institutional Repositories</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a primer to describe the purpose of IRs and their technical requirements but not using specific hardware or software. • Investigate the current state of linked data in the Canadian context.
<p>3) Tools and applications</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are a few sources that mention different tools and applications, but there is no comprehensive information available on this topic. 	<p>3) Tools and applications</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review or catalogue various recommended tools and applications deemed useful at different points of the data lifecycle (and for different disciplines).
<p>4) IT infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There seems to be insufficient storage for publishing big data outputs. • There is also insufficient storage for active (also called working) data; as distinct from repositories for publishing and sharing data. • Infrastructure to connect active, repository, and archival storage is needed. • Repositories with unique features to support deposit of sensitive data that can't be shared but should be securely kept for a period of time would be useful. 	<p>4) IT infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investigate ways to make the publication of big data easier (Compute Canada is a potential partner in this). • Investigate opportunities to increase active data storage, particularly for big data. • Investigate opportunities to connect infrastructure, supporting active, repository, and archival storage. • Conduct a needs assessment of repository features necessary to support sensitive data.
<p>5) High performance computing centre/network</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a gap in examined information available worldwide and in Canada. 	<p>5) High performance computing centre/network</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investigate and determine RDM needs related to HPCs. • Create training materials on data management practices that are HPC specific (and possibly assist in the creation of the resources).
<p>6) Trusted digital repository (TDR)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Few repositories have formal designations as Trusted Digital Repositories. 	<p>6) Trusted digital repository (TDR)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investigate current state of TDR certification of Canadian data repositories. • Investigate opportunities for educating and supporting repositories in becoming certified with recognized bodies such as: CoreTrustSeal, Trusted Repository Audit Checklist (TRAC) and ISO 16363 (also known as The Trusted Digital Repository Checklist (TDR)).

Taxonomy

Curation

File formats

The layout of a file in terms of how the data within the file are organized. A program that uses the data in a file must be able to recognize and possibly access data within the file. A particular file format is often indicated as part of a file's name by a filename extension (suffix). Examples include: Word documents (.doc), Web text pages (.htm or .html), Web page images (.gif and .jpg), Adobe Postscript files (.ps), Adobe Acrobat files (.pdf), Executable programs (.exe), Multimedia files (.mp3 and others). Preferred formats are those designated by a data repository for which the digital content is maintained. Usually, preferred formats are the de facto standard employed by a particular community.

Original source: Data file format. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from https://dictionary.casrai.org/Data_file_format

Privacy

In a legal context: A broad concept that (in Canadian law) encompasses personal privacy (protection of one's physical self), territorial privacy (protection of one's private physical space), and informational privacy (protection of information about oneself and one's activities).

Original source: Privacy [Def. 2]. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from <https://dictionary.casrai.org/Privacy>

Security

Freedom from danger or threat. With reference to encryption, or telecommunications or computer systems: the state of being protected from unauthorized access; freedom from the risk of being intercepted, decoded, tapped, etc.

Original source: Security, n. [Def. 2e]. July 2018. In *OED Online*. Retrieved from <http://www.oed.com/view/Entry/174661>

Storage and backup

Storage: The placing or keeping of data and instructions in a device from which they can be retrieved as needed.

Original source: Storage, n. [Def. 2d]. July 2018. In *OED Online*. Retrieved from www.oed.com/view/Entry/190925 ;

Backup: To provide back-up for; to make a duplicate copy of (a file, program, etc.), esp. to safeguard against loss or corruption of the original.

Original source: Back, v. [Def. 22d]. July 2018. In *OED Online*. Retrieved from <http://www.oed.com/view/Entry/14335>

Preservation and archiving

Preservation: An activity within archiving in which specific items of data are maintained over time so that they can still be accessed and understood through changes in technology.

Original source: Preservation. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from <https://dictionary.casrai.org/Preservation>

Archiving: A curation activity that ensures that data are properly selected, stored, and can be accessed, and for which logical and physical integrity are maintained over time, including security and authenticity.

Archiving. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from <https://dictionary.casrai.org/Archiving>

Data management plans

A formal statement describing how research data will be managed and documented throughout a research project and the terms regarding the subsequent deposit of the data with a data repository for long-term management and preservation.

Original source: Data management plan. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from https://dictionary.casrai.org/Data_management_plan

Costing

Estimation of the costs involved in manufacturing a product, providing a service, etc.

Original source: Costing, n.2. July 2018. In *OED Online*. Retrieved from <http://www.oed.com/view/Entry/42343>

Data curation lifecycle

A curation lifecycle model documents the relationships between all the stages in the existence of digital information, to enable active management of the resource over time thus maintaining accessibility and usability.

Original source: Digital Curation Centre. n.d. Glossary: Curation lifecycle model. Retrieved November 15, 2018, from <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/digital-curation/glossary>

Data collection and analysis

Includes all activities involved in the planning, collecting, processing, analysis and maintenance of data in the original research project. Among these activities are selecting a study design, constructing instruments for data collection, conducting data collection/creation, performing data editing/verification/validation, analyzing data, backing up data versions and preparing and tagging metadata.

Original source: Data production. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from https://dictionary.casrai.org/Data_production

Metadata

Literally, "data about data"; data that defines and describes the characteristics of other data, used to improve both business and technical understanding of data and data-related processes.

Original source: Metadata. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from <https://dictionary.casrai.org/Metadata>

Metadata acquisition/harvesting

The aggregation of metadata records from multiple content providers into a single database - while the full-text files remain at the originating archives. Metadata harvesting services were developed to improve the exposure of certain types of resources that present special retrieval problems, specifically, content that is stored in a databases or repositories that cannot be penetrated by the spiders and robots employed by search engines. Metadata harvesting services often employ the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH), which allows repositories to expose their metadata to these harvesters.

Original source: Metadata harvesting. January 2006. *Toward a Canadian Digital Information Strategy: Mapping the Current Situation in Canada*. Library and Archives Canada. Retrieved from <http://www.collectionscanada.gc.ca/obj/012018/f2/012018-3200-e.pdf>

Versioning

Control over time of data, computer code, software, and documents that allows for the ability to revert to a previous revision, which is critical for data traceability, tracking edits, and correcting mistakes.

Original source: Version control. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from https://dictionary.casrai.org/Version_control

Migration

A means of overcoming technological obsolescence by transferring digital resources from one hardware/software generation to the next. The purpose of migration is to preserve the intellectual content of digital objects and to retain the ability for clients to retrieve, display, and otherwise use them in the face of constantly changing technology.

Original source: Migration. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from <https://dictionary.casrai.org/Migration>

Data ingestion

The process of obtaining, importing, and processing data for later use or storage in a database.

Original source: Data ingestion. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from https://dictionary.casrai.org/Data_ingestion

Digitization

The process of creating digital files by scanning or otherwise converting analogue materials. The resulting digital copy, or digital surrogate, would then be classed as digital material and then subject to the same broad challenges involved in preserving access to it, as "born digital" materials.

Original source: Digital Preservation Coalition. n.d. Glossary: Digitisation. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://www.dpconline.org/handbook/glossary>

Selection and appraisal for retention

The process of making decisions regarding the continued possession of information. The objectives are to choose appropriate items and to keep important information for future use or reference, to organize information so it can be searched and accessed at a later date, and to dispose of information that is no longer needed. Both the value of data over time, and regulations to which the data may be subject must be considered.

Modified from source: Data retention policy. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from https://dictionary.casrai.org/Data_retention_policy

Data Sharing and Reuse

Data sharing

The practice of making data available for reuse. This may be done, for example, by depositing the data in a repository, through data publication.

Original source: Data sharing. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from https://dictionary.casrai.org/Data_sharing

Data reuse

Use of data content outside of its original intention.

Modified from source: Re-use. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from <https://dictionary.casrai.org/Re-use>

Data citation

Offers proper recognition to authors as well as permanent identification through the use of global persistent identifiers in place of URLs which can change frequently. Use of universal numerical fingerprints (UNFs) guarantees to the scholarly community that future researchers will be able to verify that data retrieved is identical to that used in a publication decades earlier, even if it has changed storage media, operating systems, hardware, and statistical program format. Data citation is provided in a similar way that researchers routinely include bibliographic references to traditionally published resources.

Original source: Data citation. August 2015. In The CASRAI Dictionary. Retrieved from https://dictionary.casrai.org/Data_citation

Metrics

A system or standard of measurement; a criterion or set of criteria stated in quantifiable terms for the measurement of research output or impact.

Modified from source: Metric, n. [Def. 4]. July 2018. In *OED Online*. Retrieved from <http://www.oed.com/view/Entry/117657>

Attribution

The action of ascribing a work or remark to a particular author, artist or person. For example, giving credit to data contributors, software developers, etc.

Modified from source: Attribution, n. [Def. 1.1]. n.d. In *Oxford Dictionaries.com*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/attribution>

Visualization

The representation of an object, situation, or set of information as a chart or other image.

Original source: Visualization, n. [Def. 1]. n.d. In *Oxford Dictionaries*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/visualization>

Discoverability

The quality or fact of being discoverable; capability of being discovered, found, ascertained, etc. In recent use esp. with reference to the use of online search engines.

Source. Discoverability, n. July 2018. In *OED Online*. Retrieved from <http://www.oed.com/view/Entry/54006>

Data journals and data papers

Data journals: Publications whose primary purpose is to expose datasets. They enable the author to focus on the data itself, rather than producing an extensive analysis of the data which occurs in the traditional journal model.

Original source: Australian National Data Service. n.d. Data and journals. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://www.ands.org.au/working-with-data/publishing-and-reusing-data/data-journals>

Data papers: A data paper is a document describing a dataset, published in a peer-reviewed journal. They thoroughly describe datasets, and do not usually include any interpretation or discussion (an exception may be discussion of different methods to collect the data, e.g.). Some data papers are published in a distinct “Data Papers” section of a well-established journal (see this article in Ecology, for example). It is becoming more common, however, to see these papers published in journals that exclusively focus on the publication of datasets.

Modified from sources: Global Biodiversity Information Facility. n.d. Data papers. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://www.gbif.org/data-papers>; and Oregon State University Libraries. November 2018. Research Data Services: Data Papers & Journals. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://guides.library.oregonstate.edu/research-data-services/data-management-data-papers-journals>

Data repositories

(as distinct from institutional repositories, defined below)

A digital repository that preserves, manages, and provides access to many types of data and supporting materials in a variety of formats. Materials in digital data repositories are curated to enable search, discovery, and reuse. There must be sufficient control for the digital material to be authentic, reliable, accessible and usable on a continuing basis.

Modified from source: Repository. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from <https://dictionary.casrai.org/Repository>

Permanent identifiers

A long-lasting reference to a digital object that gives information about that object regardless what happens to it. Developed to address “link rot,” a persistent identifier can be resolved to provide an appropriate representation of an object whether that objects changes its online location or goes offline.

Original source: Research Data Canada. n.d. Original RDC Glossary: Persistent identifier. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://www.rdc-drc.ca/glossary/original-rdc-glossary>

Services

Service development

Development of a system for supporting needs related to the provision of research data management services.

Definition composed by RIEG.

Assessment and evaluation

Assessment: The systematic process of establishing outcomes, explaining how those outcomes will be measured, collecting data, and analyzing / reviewing those data to make changes and improvements.

Original source: Winston-Salem State University. n.d. Assessment Glossary: Assessment. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://www.wssu.edu/about/assessment-and-research/niloa/assessment-glossary.html>

Evaluation: Evaluation is a decision about significance, value, or quality of something, based on careful study of its good and bad features.

Original source: Evaluation. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from <https://dictionary.casrai.org/Evaluation>

Training and education

Training: Sustained instruction and practice (given or received) in an art, profession, occupation, or procedure, with a view to proficiency in it.

Original source: Training, n. [Def. 3c]. July 2016. In *OED Online*. Retrieved from www.oed.com/view/Entry/204425

Education: The systematic instruction, teaching, or training in various academic and non-academic subjects given to or received, typically at a school; the course of scholastic instruction a person receives in his or her lifetime.

Modified from source: Education, n. [Def. 4a]. July 2018. In *OED Online*. Retrieved from www.oed.com/view/Entry/59584

Outreach

The activity of an organization in making contact and fostering relations with people unconnected with it, esp. for the purpose of support or education and for increasing awareness of the organization's aims or message; the fact or extent of this activity.

Original source: Outreach, n. [Def. 2b]. July 2018. In *OED Online*. Retrieved from <http://www.oed.com/view/Entry/133882>

RDM consultation

A meeting with an research data management expert, in order to seek advice.

Modified from source: Consultation, n. [Def. 1.1]. n.d. In *Oxford Dictionaries*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/consultation>

Data purchasing

Using funds to acquire data for the use of a researcher or for inclusion in a library collection.

Definition composed by RIEG.

Developing strategic plan

The creation of high-level organizational objectives, usually designed to be achieved over a set length of time, and which typically include a statement of direction or vision, stated goals or actions to be accomplished, and measures or indicators of success.

Modified from sources: Strategy. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from <https://dictionary.casrai.org/Strategy> ; and Taylor, Anthony. January 2015. What is the strategic planning process. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://www.smestrategy.net/blog/what-is-the-strategic-planning-process>

Institutional support

Intra-organizational assistance for the management, fiscal needs, space, personnel, and logistics related to the provision of research data management.

Modified from sources: Institution. 2008. In *West's Encyclopedia of American Law*, edition 2. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://legal-dictionary.thefreedictionary.com/institutional> ; and University of Wisconsin System. N.d. Institutional Support - Functional Definition. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://wisconsin.edu/financial-administration/accounting-and-budget-control/chart-of-accounts/program-1-institutional-support>

Policy and Law

Compliance

Conformance with a law or regulation.

Original source: Compliance. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from <https://dictionary.casrai.org/Compliance>

Ethics

Moral principles that govern a person's behaviour or the conducting of an activity governed by policies and regulations set forth by research ethics board.

Modified from source : Ethics, n. [Def. 1]. n.d. In Oxford Dictionaries. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/ethics>

Informed Consent

Refers to a person's agreement to allow personal data to be provided for research and statistical purposes. Agreement is based on full exposure of the facts the person needs to make the decision intelligently, including awareness of any risks involved, of uses and users of the data, and of alternatives to providing the data.

Original source: Informed Consent. November 2005. In *OECD Glossary of Statistical Terms*. Retrieved from <https://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=6933>

Intellectual property

Chiefly Law property (such as patents, trademarks, and copyright material) which is the product of invention or creativity, and does not exist in a tangible, physical form. Intellectual property includes inventions, new technologies, original software, novel designs, and creative works. These assets have value in the marketplace and are protected by government intellectual property laws.

Modified from sources: Intellectual property, n. July 2018. In *OED Online*. Retrieved from www.oed.com/view/Entry/97387 ; and Government of Canada. October 2016. Intellectual assets. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://www.ic.gc.ca/eic/site/cipointernet-internetopic.nsf/eng/wr03585.html>

Deposit licenses

A licence agreement establishing the terms and conditions of use of a data collection. This is a legal document which sets out rights and responsibilities for depositors and distributors.

Modified from source: UK Data Archive. n.d. Terms and conditions data deposit. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <http://data-archive.ac.uk/conditions/data-deposit>

User licenses

A formal statement issued by the holder of the rights to a particular work (e.g. a database), giving permission to use the work in certain specified ways. Licences for data fall into two broad categories: Traditional data sharing or collaboration agreements, which grant rights only to specific individuals or entities. Open' licenses, which grant rights to anyone, often subject to certain minimal conditions like attribution of the data's owner. Commonly used open licences for data include Creative Commons and Open Data Commons licences.

Original source: University of Oxford. n.d. Rights and licensing. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <http://researchdata.ox.ac.uk/home/sharing-your-data/rights-licensing/>

Institutional policy

A principle or course of action adopted or proposed as desirable, advantageous, or expedient; specifically pertaining to institutions outlining the basis for activities and conduct, as well as the relationship between the organization and its components. These policies are usually framed within an institutional mandate or mission.

Modified from sources: Policy, n.1. [Def. 4]. July 2018. In *OED Online*. Retrieved from <http://www.oed.com/view/Entry/146842> ; and The World Bank. n.d. Institutional policy. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <http://web.worldbank.org/archive/website00236B/WEB/INSTITUT.HTM>

Funding policy

A principle or course of action adopted or proposed as desirable, advantageous, or expedient; specifically pertaining to actions mandated by agencies providing funding for research.

Modified from source: Policy, n.1. [Def. 4]. July 2018. In *OED Online*. Retrieved from <http://www.oed.com/view/Entry/146842>

Journal policy

A principle or course of action adopted or proposed as desirable, advantageous, or expedient; specifically pertaining to journal and publisher requirements for authors.

Modified from source: Policy, n.1. [Def. 4]. July 2018. In *OED Online*. Retrieved from <http://www.oed.com/view/Entry/146842>

Fields of Research

Arts and humanities

Arts: The theory and practice of the visual arts as a subject of study or examination

Original source: Art, n.1. [Def. 8b]. July 2018. In *OED Online*. Retrieved from <http://www.oed.com/view/Entry/11125>

Humanities: The branch of learning concerned with human culture; the academic subjects collectively comprising this branch of learning, as history, literature, ancient and modern languages, law, philosophy, art, and music.

Original source: Humanity, n. [Def. 2b]. July 2018. In *OED Online*. Retrieved from <http://www.oed.com/view/Entry/89280>

Digital humanities

An academic field concerned with the application of computational tools and methods to traditional humanities disciplines such as literature, history, and philosophy.

Original source: Digital humanities, n. n.d. In *Oxford Dictionaries*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/digital_humanities

Health and medical sciences

Health sciences: The health sciences study all aspects of health, disease and healthcare. This field of study aims to develop knowledge, interventions and technology for use in healthcare to improve the treatment of patients.

Original source: SpringerNature. n.d. Health sciences. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://www.nature.com/subjects/health-sciences>

Medical sciences: The branch of science concerned with the study of the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of disease.

Original source: Digital humanities, n. [Def. 1]. n.d. In *Oxford Dictionaries*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/medical_science

Physical and applied sciences

Physical sciences: any of the branches of science concerned with inanimate matter and energy (e.g. astronomy, physics, chemistry, geology); spec. physics; (also) these sciences collectively.

Original source: Physical science, n. July 2018. In *OED Online*. Retrieved from <http://www.oed.com/view/Entry/143120>

Applied sciences: The application of existing scientific knowledge to practical applications, like technology or inventions

Original source: Wikipedia contributors. October 2018. Applied science. In *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Applied_science&oldid=862907215

Social sciences

The study of human society and social relationships; a subject within this field, as economics, politics, sociology, etc.

Original source: Social science, n. July 2018. In *OED Online*. Retrieved from <http://www.oed.com/view/Entry/183756>

Interdisciplinary research

A study undertaken by scholars from two or more distinct scientific disciplines. The research is based upon a conceptual model that links or integrates theoretical frameworks from those disciplines, uses study design and methodology that is not limited to any one field, and requires the use of perspectives and skills of the involved disciplines throughout multiple phases of the research process.

Original source: Inter-disciplinary. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from <https://dictionary.casrai.org/Inter-disciplinary>

Types of Data

Administrative data

Information collected primarily for administrative, and not research purposes. It includes profiles and curriculum vitae of researchers, the scope and impact of research projects, funding, citations, and research outcomes. This type of data is collected by government departments and other organisations for the purposes of registration, transaction and record keeping, usually during the delivery of a service. These data are also recognized as having research value.

Original source: Administrative data. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from https://dictionary.casrai.org/Administrative_data

Qualitative data

Data describing the attributes or properties that an object possesses. The properties are categorized into classes that may be assigned numeric values. However, there is no significance to the data values themselves, they simply represent attributes of the object concerned.

Original source: Qualitative data. January 2004. In *OECD Glossary of Statistical Terms*. Retrieved from <https://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=3494>

Quantitative data

Data expressing a certain quantity, amount or range. Usually, there are measurement units associated with the data, e.g. metres, in the case of the height of a person. It makes sense to set boundary limits to such data, and it is also meaningful to apply arithmetic operations to the data.

Original source: Quantitative data. January 2006. In *OECD Glossary of Statistical Terms*. Retrieved from <https://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=2219>

Big data

An evolving term that describes any voluminous amount of structured, semi-structured and unstructured data that have the potential to be mined for information.

Original source: Big data [Def. 1]. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from https://dictionary.casrai.org/Big_data

Open data

Structured data that are accessible, machine-readable, usable, intelligible, and freely shared. Open data can be freely used, re-used, built on, and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.

Original source: Open data. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from https://dictionary.casrai.org/Open_data

Sensitive and confidential data

Sensitive data: Data that can be used to identify an individual, species, object, or location that introduces a risk of discrimination, harm, or unwanted attention.

Original source: Australian National Data Service. n.d. Safely sharing sensitive data. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://www.ands.org.au/working-with-data/sensitive-data/sharing-sensitive-data>

Confidential data: Data which are subject to confidentiality clauses.

Original source: Confidential data. June 2013. In *OECD Glossary of Statistical Terms*. Retrieved from <https://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?!D=5124>

Linked data

Data where relationships/connections between them are available to allow easy data access. A typical case of a large Linked dataset is DBPedia (<http://dbpedia.org/>), which essentially makes the content of Wikipedia available in RDF. This related collection of interrelated datasets is stored on the Web and available via a common format -RDF.

Original source: Linked open data. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from https://dictionary.casrai.org/Linked_open_data

Stakeholders

Librarians and data stewards

Librarian: A person who works professionally in a library, providing access to information and sometimes social or technical programming to users. Some librarians have functional roles related to research and data management, conducting curation and metadata-related work, or providing support services such as finding, using, and retrieving, collecting data for use in secondary analysis.

Modified from sources: Data librarian. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from https://dictionary.casrai.org/Data_librarian ; and Wikipedia contributors. November 2018. Librarian. In *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*. Retrieved November 15, 2018, from <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Librarian&oldid=869142118>

Data steward: Data stewards, along with principal investigators, provide support for: (a) Data collection, data integration, or reuse of existing data; (b) Review of data quality; (c) Description of scientific workflow/process; (d) Provision of standards-compliant metadata; and, (e) Submission of data and data productions. Data stewards are responsible for, and Principle Investigators are consulted and informed on: (a) Preservation of data and data products; and, (b) Provision of formats (e.g., web services, NetCDF, etc.) for data discovery and integration.

Modified from Data steward. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from https://dictionary.casrai.org/Data_steward

Service and infrastructure providers

Any type of organized corporation or society that provides services or infrastructure to aid the management and dissemination of research data. For example: ORCID, Compute Canada, DataCite

Definition composed by RIEG.

Policy makers and administrators

Policy maker: A person, office or organization responsible for or involved in formulating policies,

Original source: Policymaker. n.d. n *Oxford Dictionaries.com*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/policymaker>

Administrator: A person or office responsible for carrying out the administration of a business or organization.

Original source: Administrator. n.d. n *Oxford Dictionaries.com*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/administrator>

Faculty and researchers

Faculty: The teaching or research staff of a group of university departments viewed as a body.

Original source: Faculty [Def. 2.1]. n.d. *Oxford Dictionaries.com*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/faculty>

Researcher: A person who carries out academic or scientific research.

Original source: Researcher [Def. 1]. n.d. *Oxford Dictionaries.com*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/researcher>

Graduate Students

A student with a bachelor's degree from a university who is studying or doing research at a more advanced level.

Modified from source: Graduate student, n. n.d. In *Collins English Dictionary*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/us/dictionary/english/graduate-student>

Undergraduates

A student at a university who is studying for a bachelor's degree.

Modified from source: Undergraduate, n. n.d. In *Collins English Dictionary*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/us/dictionary/english/undergraduate>

iSchools/Library Schools

Post-secondary program, often at the graduate degree level, that is committed to understanding the role of information in society. Often a required program for professionals entering library and information management fields, and may be certified by professional associations (e.g. American Library Association).

Definition composed by RIEG.

Higher education institutions

Colleges, universities, polytechnics, etc. that provide education and training.

Modified from source: Higher education. n.d. In *Collins English Dictionary*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/us/dictionary/english/higher-education>

Funding bodies

Government or organization entities that provide money for a particular purpose.

Modified from source: Funding. n.d. In *Collins English Dictionary*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/us/dictionary/english/funding>

Journals and publishers

Journal: A scholarly or academic publication, that regularly publishes content about a particular subject.

Modified from source: Journal, n. [Def. C1]. n.d. In *Cambridge Dictionary*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/journal>

Publisher: A person or company that produces and sells books, magazines, newspapers, software, etc.

Original source: Publisher, n. n.d. In *Cambridge Dictionary*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/publisher>

National or regional networks

A group, system, etc. of interconnected or cooperating entities acting together at the national or regional level. E.g. Portage, Australian National Data Service, Digital Curation Centre.

Modified from source: Network [Def. 2]. n.d. In *Collins English Dictionary*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/us/dictionary/english/higher-education>

Information Technologies

Cloud computing

A large-scale distributed computing paradigm that is driven by economies of scale, in which a pool of abstracted, virtualized, dynamically- scalable, managed computing power, storage, platforms and services are delivered on demand to external customers over the Internet.

Original source: Cloud computing. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from https://dictionary.casrai.org/Cloud_computing

Institutional Repositories

A university-based institutional repository is a set of services that a university offers to the members of its community for the management and dissemination of digital data and supporting materials created by the institution and its community members. It is most essentially an organizational commitment to the stewardship of these digital materials, including long-term preservation where appropriate, as well as organization and access or distribution.

Modified from source: Lynch, C.A. February 2003. Institutional repositories: Essential infrastructure for scholarship in the digital age [PDF file]. *ARL Bimonthly Report*, 226: 1-7. Retrieved from <https://www.cni.org/wp-content/uploads/2003/02/arl-br-226-Lynch-IRs-2003.pdf>

Tools and applications

Software tool: A program that is employed in the development, repair, or enhancement of other programs or of computing hardware. Software tools can assist in all activities of all phases of the software life cycle, including management and quality-assurance activities. Thus a comprehensive set would address such issues as requirements specification, design, validation, configuration control, and project management.

Modified from source: Software tool. n.d. In *Encyclopedia.com* (originally published by *Oxford University Press*, 2004). Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://www.encyclopedia.com/computing/dictionaries-thesauruses-pictures-and-press-releases/software-tool>

Application package: A collection of programs or modules that is directed at some generic application and can be tailored (perhaps with some additions) to the needs of a specific instance of that application.

Original source : Application package. n.d. In *Encyclopedia.com* (originally published by *Oxford University Press*, 2004). Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://www.encyclopedia.com/computing/dictionaries-thesauruses-pictures-and-press-releases/application-package>

IT infrastructure

The term infrastructure in an information technology (IT) context refers to an enterprise's entire collection of hardware, software, networks, data centers, facilities and related equipment used to develop, test, operate, monitor, manage and/or support information technology services.

Original source: Infrastructure. n.d. In *Webopedia*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://www.webopedia.com/TERM/I/infrastructure.html>

High performance computing centre/network

Data centres or networks devoted to high performance computing, which is “the use of super computers and parallel processing techniques for solving complex computational problems.

Modified from source: High-performance computing (HPC). n.d. In *Techopedia*. Retrieved November 15, 2018 from <https://www.techopedia.com/definition/4595/high-performance-computing-hpc>

Trusted digital repository (TDR)

An infrastructure component that provides reliable, long-term access to managed digital resources. It stores, manages, and curates digital objects and returns their bit streams when a request is issued. Trusted repositories undergo regular assessments according to a set of rules such as defined by Data Seal of Approval (DSA) or TRAC (ISO 16363).

Original source: Trusted digital repository. August 2015. In *The CASRAI Dictionary*. Retrieved from https://dictionary.casrai.org/Trusted_Digital_Repository

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